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New Class of High Speed Steels for Aero Rolling Bearings

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Abstract:	<p>The load carrying demands for rolling bearing components are constantly increasing and the bearing materials are required to be progressively durable. The industry is familiar with incremental rolling bearing material improvements and these are well documented. The testing of powder metallurgy (PM) high speed steel (HSS) grades started in the 1970's. The introduction of high cleanliness steel melting, refining and powder atomization, with consolidation by cold and hot isostatic pressing (HIP), resulted in a significant improvement in the metallurgical integrity of PM steel HSS's. Cobalt free HSS based on the M62 composition steel (VIMCRU 20) yielded improvements in the rolling bearing function properties. The push for higher load capacities, particularly to support the use of ceramic rolling elements, meant that a new ultra-high hardness class of steel is desired. Cobalt alloying of HSSs is well established for tooling but not for bearings. A HSS with a 10% cobalt addition has been tested with the aim to use it for demanding aerospace applications. In this paper, the microstructure of the steel (AMS 6560) has been investigated together with its rolling bearing functional properties. The obtained results are compared to the industry standard VIM-VAR M50 (AMS 6490).</p>

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ABSTRACT

The load carrying demands for rolling bearing components are constantly increasing and the bearing materials are required to be progressively durable. The industry is familiar with incremental rolling bearing material improvements and these are well documented. The testing of powder metallurgy (PM) high speed steel (HSS) grades started in the 1970's. The introduction of high cleanliness steel melting, refining and powder atomization, with consolidation by cold and hot isostatic pressing (HIP), resulted in a significant improvement in the metallurgical integrity of PM steel HSS's. Cobalt free HSS based on the M62 composition steel (VIMCRU 20) yielded improvements in the rolling bearing function properties.

The push for higher load capacities, particularly to support the use of ceramic rolling elements, meant that a new ultra-high hardness class of steel is desired. Cobalt alloying of HSSs is well established for tooling but not for bearings. A HSS with a 10% cobalt addition has been tested with the aim to use it for demanding aerospace applications. In this paper, the microstructure of the steel (AMS 6560) has been investigated together with its rolling bearing functional properties. The obtained results are compared to the industry standard VIM-VAR M50 (AMS 6490).

Keywords

Aerospace bearing material; Powder metallurgy; AMS 6560; Rolling contact fatigue; Single-ball test; Multi contact testing

Introduction

Extensive literature exists on steelmaking technologies for rolling bearings with steel cleanliness being the major consideration to avoid early rolling contact fatigue spalling failures which are initiated due to the stress concentrations at non-metallic inclusions. The introduction of vacuum induction melting, in combination with vacuum arc refining in the 1980's, significantly improved the reliability of high speed steels for aero bearing applications. The main aero bearing steel development events are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Aero Bearing Steel Development Events.

The first known test results of powder metallurgy, applied for high temperature steel (HSS) steelmaking, is from a paper published in 1982 [1]. Subsequently, the high cleanliness PM grade of M62 was developed for demanding applications [2] (Figure 1) and established as the

Aerospace Material Specification (AMS) 6558.

The AMS 6558 was initially tested under the designation REX 20 [3] and the technology gained acceptance when vacuum induction melting (VIM) was introduced to improve the metallurgical cleanliness (VIMCRU 20). The AMS 6558 steel is a cobalt-free HSS.

The benefits of cobalt additions in increasing the secondary hardness are well known in HSS steelmaking [4] and HSS with 10% cobalt are commonly used in tooling applications. The commercial steel ASP 2060 has been reported to be a suitable steel for rolling bearings with a potential to achieve a hardness approaching HRC 70 [5,6]. A steel with a heat-treated hardness of 70 HRC has as huge potential for high temperature, highly loaded, rolling bearings. The metallurgy and rolling bearing functional properties in respect of toughness and rolling contact fatigue strength are described in this paper for AMS 6560 and compared to the industry baseline VIM-VAR M50 (AMS 6490) steel.

STEEL COMPOSITIONS

The AMS alloy chemical composition specifications of the two HSS mentioned in this paper are listed in table 1:

	AMS 6490 (M50)	AMS 6560 (ASP 2060)
C	0.77- 0.85	2.25 – 2.35
Mn	Max. 0.35	0.10 – 0.50
Si	Max. 0.25	0.40 – 0.80
Cr	3.75 – 4.25	3.75 – 4.50
Mo	4.00 – 4.50	6.50 – 7.50
V	0.90 – 1.10	6.25 – 6.75
Co	Max. 0.25	10.0 – 11.0
W	Max. 0.25	6.0 – 7.0

Table 1. HSS compositions according to AMS specifications (wt.%).

AMS 6560 STEELMAKING

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3 The steelmaking for AMS 6560 steel falls into two categories namely; vacuum induction melting
4 by carbon de-oxidation or refining in electro slag heated (ESH) tundish's [7] using either
5 induction stirring or argon bubbling agitation. The details of the processes of powder
6 atomization, powder storage/grading and compaction by isostatic consolidation with subsequent
7 hot forging and rolling are very important for the final metallurgical integrity. Suitable quality
8 controls are required to exclude the possibility of cross-contamination from powders from
9 different steel grades as well as optimal cleanliness conditions in the melting, powder production
10 and pressing plants.
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24 **MICRO CLEANLINESS**

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27 High metallurgical cleanliness is essential for quality assurance and the application ranges for
28 HSS. Correctly produced VIM-VAR steels used in aero bearings are very clean as compared to
29 standard air melted bearing steel grades but it is very challenging to reliably quantify the micro
30 cleanliness. The VIM-VAR M50 (AMS 6490) and the AMS 6560 are assessed with the ASTM
31 E45 test method. AMS 6490 is assessed with the method D while AMS 6560 follows the method
32 A. A major difference between method D and method A is that in method A the metallographer
33 scans the test field to rate the worst field whereas in method D each field must be viewed to rate
34 the inclusions. If the results of method D are used to give the rating for the worst field, as in
35 method A, the compliance of the AMS 6560 may be compared with the VIM-VAR bearing steel
36 AMS specification limits. This comparison is shown in Figure 2 where it can be seen that the can
37 comply with the AMS micro cleanliness requirements if produced using state-of-the-art PM-HIP
38 process methodologies. The Figure 2 shows indeed that the cleanliness rating of AMS 6560 steel
39 (produced with the ESH tundish steel making method with argon bubbling) is fully compliant
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with requirements and limits of ASTM E45 for various VIM-VAR steels (M50, 52100, P675 and M50NiL).

Figure 2. Comparison of AMS 6560 Cleanliness (evaluated by SKF: red dot/line) with VIM-VAR Bearing Steel Limits (ASTM E45 limits represented by coloured markers).

HEAT TREATMENT AND MICROSTRUCTURE

The composition of AMS 6560 is designed as a secondary hardening steel and the heat treatment and secondary hardening information is given in the ASP 2060 data sheet [8]. As with all HSS's, the achievable hardness is a function of the austenitization temperature and secondary hardening temperature but for bearing steels the heat treatment parameters must be selected to have as low a retained austenite content as possible, as well as to avoid a significant loss in toughness while still achieving a near maximum hardness.

The heat treatments applied for the toughness testing, washers for rolling contact fatigue (RCF) testing and the balls for the single ball “V” groove RCF tests are given in Table 2 together with the resulting hardness. One can note that the different samples (balls, flat washer and toughness test samples) are initially parts of diverse studies and have been treated in various factories in Europe and US where the heat-treatment processes are historically slightly different and resulted in marginally dissimilar hardness.

	Toughness Tests:		Washer Multi Contact RCF Tests:		Single Ball “V” Groove RCF Tests:	
	AMS 6490	AMS 6560	AMS 6490	AMS 6560	AMS 6490	AMS 6560
Austenitization:	1150°C	1150°C	1150°C	1150°C	1093°C,	1150°C
Quench:	50°C	38 to 49°C	50°C	38 to 49°C	50°C	38 to 49°C
Temper:	Triple temper 545°C	Four (4) times 560°C, 1 hour	Triple temper 545°C	Four (4) times 560°C, 1 hour	510°C, subzero treat at -79°C and triple temper at 545 to 550°C,	Triple temper at 560°C
Sub-zero treatment:	Yes - 196°C	None	Yes - 196°C	None	Yes	None
Hardness (HRC)	62.6	67.9	62.8	68.6	62.5	68

Table 2. Heat Treatment Conditions for AMS 6560 and AMS 6490 Test Materials.

The carbide distribution resulting from the applied heat treatment are shown in Figure 3 and Figure 4. In AMS 6560, the residual carbides are M_6C and MC while they are M_2C and MC in AMS 6490.

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Figure 3. Carbide distribution of Heat Treated AMS 6560 Steel.

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Figure 4. Carbide distribution of Heat Treated AMS 6490 Steel.

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The volume fraction of carbides and the mean free path distances were found to be significant microstructural variables. They will be discussed in the section on fracture toughness.

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54 TOUGHNESS

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The toughness of the AMS 6560 steel is compared to the VIM-VAR M50 (AMS 6490) industrial

standard using blunt notch impact testing, plane strain fracture toughness K_{IC} and ΔK_{th} threshold stress intensity testing. The merits of the blunt notch and K_{IC} toughness testing methodologies will be seen from the information in the following sections:

Blunt Notch Testing

The details of the blunt notch test methodology are described elsewhere [9]. The three test samples were taken in the transverse (ASTM [10] C-L) and longitudinal (ASTM L-C) orientations with the test results being shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Transverse - Longitudinal Impact Test Results.

From the results in Figure 5, the perfect isotropic properties for the PM-HIP AMS 6560 variant can be appreciated, especially compared to the directional blunt notch impact toughness properties for VIM-VAR M50.

Plain Strain Fracture Toughness (K_{IC})

Fracture toughness testing is a popular material characterisation parameter used in the evaluation

of aerospace steels. The transverse and longitudinal fracture toughness test values are plotted in Figure 6 where it can be appreciated that the K_{IC} values for VIM-VAR M50 are significantly higher than those for the AMS 6560 test steel. Moreover, for both grades, we observed that the K_{IC} value is insensitive to the material test direction.

The literature [11] has found that the microstructure-fracture toughness relationships in HSS are a function of the carbide morphology and not the matrix. The relationship given in the literature shows that the open microstructure of the VIM-VAR M50, as compared with the high volume fraction fine carbide (low mean-free path distances) microstructure of the AMS 6560 steel, will result in the observed differences in K_{IC} .

On the other hand, one can note that the M50 K_{IC} is isotropic despite the extreme difference in residual carbide in the CL and LC directions. That is an important clue showing that K_{IC} is insensitive to orientation of residual carbides. So the observed difference of K_{IC} between VIM-VAR M50 and AMS6560 is a result of matrix properties (and/or secondary carbide precipitates).

Figure 6. Transverse - Longitudinal K_{IC} Test Data.

Threshold Stress Intensity Tests (ΔK_{th}):

The literature contains information on the threshold stress intensity (ΔK_{th}) for heat-treated M50 [12]. However, no such data is known for PM-HIP HSS.

A load ratio R of 0.1 was used for the testing of the threshold stress intensity (ΔK_{th}) on the HSS test materials. The mean of two test results for each test variant are given in Table 3:

AMS 6490		AMS 6560	
C-L Transverse	L-C Longitudinal	C-L Transverse	L-C Longitudinal
3.5 (MPa. \sqrt{m})	3.8 (MPa. \sqrt{m})	3.9 (MPa. \sqrt{m})	3.7 (MPa. \sqrt{m})

Table 3. Summary of ΔK_{th} Test Results at R = 0.1.

There is not significant difference between the ΔK_{th} values for the AMS 6560 and the M50.

ROLLING CONTACT FATIGUE STRENGTH

The testing of the rolling contact fatigue (RCF) strength of new steels is an established procedure in the bearing industry. The first known discussion of the subject dates from 1946 [13]. Aerospace applications (i.e: engine Mainshaft) can be considered as medium load applications (Hertzian contact pressure about 1.8GPa are standard). Nevertheless, to obtain some failures during testing of very high capacity steels, higher pressures should be reached (from 3 to 5 GPa). Due to the application of high loads misleading conditions or non-representative failure modes may be generated in the test materials. "Pure" rolling contact conditions without bending or sliding are the ideal testing conditions. Washer and RCF ball testing are described in the following sections.

Multi Contact Washer RCF Testing

The multi contact washer RCF test methodology is described elsewhere [14]. The test load has

been kept equal for both steels, resulting in a contact pressure of 4.2 GPa for M50 and a higher contact pressure of 4.52 GPa for the powder metallurgical steel due to the higher Young's modulus ($E_{M50} \sim 206$ GPa; $E_{AMS6560} \sim 250$ GPa).

Figure 7. Schematic representation of the Multi Contact Washer RCF Testing.

The testing conditions are presented below:

- Ceramic Si_3N_4 balls 5.556 mm diameter
- Hertz maximum pressure 4.20 GPa for VIM-VAR M50; 4.52 GPa for AMS6560
- Lubricant Mil L 23699
- Oil temperature 40°C
- Spalling detection by vibration (accelerometer)
- Suspension time: 500Hrs corresponding to 1,330 million load cycles

The RCF test results are shown as a Weibull distribution plot in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Multi Contact Washer RCF Test Results – 4.2 GPa Contact Pressure for VIM-VAR M50.

Even if the Hertzian contact pressure is higher, the AMS 6560 steel has a significantly greater RCF strength than the VIM-VAR M50 test steel. The AMS 6560 L_{10} is estimated to be about 3.5 times higher than the VIM-VAR M50 L_{10} : 596 million load cycles compared to 179 million load cycles.

Single Ball “V” Groove RCF Testing

Because of the higher hardness of the AMS 6560 steel the balls had to be produced in a different way compared to the traditional M50 (AMS 6490), see Table 4.

	As Received Form:	Ball Blank Production Method:
M50 AMS 6490	16 mm ground spheroidized annealed wire	Cold heading
AMS 6560	17 mm ground to 16 mm diameter	Hot forging and spheroidize anneal

Table 4. Information on Test Ball Forming Methods.

The ball forming methods, and the isotropic properties and particularly the wire rod center metallurgical integrity, have a profound effect on the ball pole and equator RCF strengths, see Figure 9. For this reason, the observed billet center macro etch observation in the VIM-VAR AMS 6490 (M50) is relevant. Macro etching using the ASTM method A561 showed a slight indication of center darkening in the VIM-VAR AMS 6490 (M50) billet test material with no such indication in the equivalent PM-HIP AMS 6560 steel billet. This observation is relevant to the ball metallurgical integrity relationships with the rolling contact fatigue (RCF) test results.

Figure 9. Forming Flow-Lines and Carbide Directionality in Ball Headed M50.

The single ball “V” groove RCF test is a well-known testing method and the first reported single ball “V” groove RCF test on powder metallurgy balls dates from 1982 on T15 steel (1.1 C, 4.0

Cr, 5.0 V, 12 W, 5.0 Co wt.%) [15].

Figure 10. V-Groove test principle.

For the currently reported 7/8 inch balls were single ball “V” groove tested using the following conditions:

- 3.86 GPa Hertz stress for VIM-VAR M50; 4.07 GPa for AMS6560 (constant load)
- 8000 \pm 500 rpm shaft speed,
- Mobil Jet II lubrication (MIL-L-23699),
- 93.3°C lubricant temperature,
- 3.8 liter/minute oil flow rate,
- 3 μ m filtration,
- 200-hours suspension time (1,440 million load cycles),
- 25-degree angle V-rings.

The M50 ball baseline results for the applied test is shown in Figure 11. Under the test conditions the computed L_{10} for M50 is of the order of 105 million of loading cycles (so 14.6 hours of V-

Groove testing). For sixteen (16) tested balls, fourteen (14) balls failed before 200 hours and two (2) balls were suspended without failure.

Figure 11. Baseline M50 Single Ball “V” RCF Life.

The fifteen (15) AMS 6560 steel balls tested under identical test conditions (same loading, so higher contact pressure) did not fail and have survived two hundred (200) hours (= suspension criteria). Two hundred (200) test hours represent more than 1,440 million of loading cycles (blue bold line on Figure 12). Two hundred (200) test hours (suspension time) also represent about fourteen (14) times the L_{10} of M50 = 105 million of loading cycles (see Figure 12); such RCF result is equivalent to the best quality silicon nitride balls [16].

Figure 12. Comparison of Single Ball “V” Groove RCF Tests with the Weibull analysis of the baseline M50 balls (red line and dots) and the suspension cycles of the AMS 6560 balls (blue bold line, no ball failure).

DISCUSSION

A technology checklist is appropriate when evaluating the suitability of new steel technologies for rolling bearings. The AMS 6560 in the selected heat treatment condition is appraised in such a checklist in Table 5.

Parameters:	AMS 6560 Properties
Steelmaking and metallurgical cleanliness and integrity (micro porosity)	High cleanliness PM steelmaking with consolidation using HIP and forging. ASTM E45 method A limits within AMS limits for VIM-VAR aerospace quality steel.
Static capacity – RT hardness and resistance to superficial indentation	Subsurface hardness of minimum ~68 HRC, Static capacity >4.7 GPa (for Plastic residual deformation/Rolling element deformation dp/D of 0.0001).
Static capacity - hot hardness	Approximately 59 HRC at 350°C
Dimensional stability	Retained austenite content: less than 2% [17]

Sub-surface contact fatigue	Approximately 3.5 times higher L_{10} RCF life than AMS 6490 *(M50) under clean well lubricated room temperature running conditions and high pressure conditions.
Surface distress	Free of large MC carbides therefore improved raceway surfaces.
Structural toughness – isotropic properties	Isotropic longitudinal – transverse properties with a transverse toughness slightly higher than AMS 6490 (M50). Reduced plane strain fracture toughness in longitudinal and transverse test directions.
Compressive surface stress	Desirable
Physical properties [8]	Elastic modulus = 250 GPa, Poisson's ratio = ~0.30, Density = >7.9 g/cm ³ , Thermal expansion coefficient 25 to 400°C = 10.6 mm/mm/°C.10 ⁻⁶ , Specific heat 20°C = 0.420 J/g.K, Thermal conductivity 20°C = 0.24 W/cm.K, Thermal stability (max. 2 vol.% retained austenite).

Table 5. Bearing Steel Technology Functional Property Checklist.

CONCLUSIONS

The extremely high hardness achievable in the AMS 6560 steel resulting in a high static loading capabilities, places the steel among the best high performances and high temperature bearing steels. The AMS 6560 is also an excellent steel for demanding applications where lesser steels fail due to fretting failure. Moreover, the AMS 6560 has demonstrated a very high rolling contact fatigue resistance for the bearing ring raceway or the rolling elements, especially in comparison to the baseline AMS 6490 (M50) steel. This high capacity rolling element steel can offer a tougher alternative to ceramics (an average value of the toughness of ceramics is $K_{IC} = 7$ MPa.m^{1/2} [18]).

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Aero Bearing Steel Development Events.

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Comparison of AMS 6560 Cleanliness (evaluated by SKF: red dot/line) with VIM-VAR Bearing Steel Limits (ASTM E45 limits represented by coloured markers).

82x53mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Carbide distribution of Heat Treated AMS 6560 Steel.

33x25mm (300 x 300 DPI)

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Carbide distribution of Heat Treated AMS 6490 Steel.
34x25mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Transverse - Longitudinal Impact Test Results.

42x24mm (300 x 300 DPI)

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Transverse - Longitudinal K1C Test Data.

42x24mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Schematic representation of the Multi Contact Washer RCF Testing.

56x20mm (300 x 300 DPI)

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Multi Contact Washer RCF Test Results – 4.2 GPa Contact Pressure for VIM-VAR M50.
79x63mm (300 x 300 DPI)

33 Forming Flow-Lines and Carbide Directionality in Ball Headed M50.

34 68x53mm (300 x 300 DPI)

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Groove test principle.

34x29mm (300 x 300 DPI)

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Baseline M50 Single Ball "V" RCF Life.
106x69mm (300 x 300 DPI)

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Comparison of Single Ball "V" Groove RCF Tests with the Weibull analysis of the baseline M50 balls (red line and dots) and the suspension cycles of the AMS 6560 balls (blue bold line, no ball failure).

106x69mm (300 x 300 DPI)